

CEMENT PRODUCTION PROCESS AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF CEMENT AND CONCRETE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7214229>

Cement production is one of the largest industries in the world. Annual world production in 2013 was approximately 4 GT (of which, about half was in China). It is produced in kilns at around 1400°C (2500°F), and approximately 750 kg (1650 lb) of CO₂ are released for each tonne (2205 lb.) that is made. This is 400 m³ (524 yd³) of gas; and CO₂ normally forms only 0.04% of air. Cement production is responsible for around 7% of worldwide greenhouse gas emissions. The only larger contributors are electricity generation and transport. Most of the CO₂ released when cement is made comes from the chemical reaction. The limestone from which it is made is calcium carbonate, and when this is heated it gives off carbon dioxide, and forms calcium oxide. Thus, while some benefit has been obtained by making the process more energy efficient, there is little scope for any further reductions.

Numerous different solutions to this problem have been proposed, including carbon capture and inventing completely new cements; but the only effective method currently used to achieve significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions is the use of cement replacements.

One process that has not been extensively investigated is carbon sequestration. In this process, the hydrated cement reacts with CO₂ in the air, slowly reversing some of the processes that took place in the kiln when the cement was made (this is the carbonation process; it also causes reinforcement corrosion, see Section 25.3.2). It is estimated that this may reduce the carbon footprint of the cement industry by 3–5%.

The cement production process is one of the most energy-consuming processes and has a strong environmental impact. The main impact on the energy consumption of cement production is the burning process of cement clinker in a rotary kiln, and the energy costs associated with burning cement clinker constitute 50-75% of cement production costs. Therefore, most of the activities in the cement industry are concerned with focusing on the process of lowering energy intensity. The use of new, energy-saving production technologies, and increasing the share of alternative fuels from waste in the process of cocombustion with coal in a rotary kiln requires the circulation of volatile components that are dangerous for the process: chlorine and sulfur. Therefore, there is a problem of managing significant amounts of the obtained byproduct.

This chapter presents the physical and chemical properties of the formed cement kiln dusts (CKDs) and the possibilities of their development in construction.

Cement is the basic material for buildings and civil engineering constructions. Portland cement, the most widely used cement in concrete construction, was patented in 1824. Cement is a fine powdery material untwining silicates of calcium, formed out of raw materials consisting calcium oxide, silica, aluminum oxide and iron oxide. India has an installed capacity of 234 million tons per year, making this is the second highest Cement producer in the whole world. As is the case in the United States, several multinational Cement producers have built up a larger share of India's Cement production industry. Among many countries India is the second highest producer of cement in the world, with 130 large cement plants and an installed capacity of 234 million ton per annum (94% of which is from large cement plants). During 2006-2007 cement production grew at a rate of 9.1% compared to the same period the previous year. However, despite this growth, India's per capita production is 115 kg per annum, well under the world average of 250 kg (World Cement 2007). The Cement manufacturing sector plays a vital role in the nation's economic development since cement is the most versatile and widely used construction material. The cement industry has made phenomenal progress in terms of volume, technology and product up gradation in recent years.

Types of cement. The cement industry has been producing a range of six main varieties of cement like PSC (Portland Blast Furnace Slag Cement), SRC (Sulphate Resisting Cement), PPC (Portland Pozzolana Cement), OPC(Ordinary Portland Cement) Oil Well Cement and White Cement, besides 53S-43S(earlier IRS-T40) for railway sleepers. Cement produced in India compulsorily conforms to Indian Standards specification issued by the Bureau of Indian Standards(BIS).These are five certified types of cement- Portland Cement, Portland blast furnance Cement, Sulphate-resisting Portland Cement, Masonry Cement and Portland pulverized fuel ash Cement (BIS, 2005).

Types of Cement Process. The cement manufacturing process involves mining, crushing, grinding of raw materials (principally limestone and clay), blending of raw meal, calcining the materials in a rotary kiln, cooling the resulting clinker, mixing the clinker with gypsum, and milling, storing, and bagging the finished cement. The raw materials used to make cement may be divided into four basic components: lime (calcareous), silica (siliceous), alumina (argillaceous), and iron (ferriferous). Approximately 1450 kilograms (kg) of dry raw materials are

required to produce one tonne of cement. Approximately 35% of the raw material weight is removed as carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water vapour. The basic chemistry of cement manufacturing process begins with the decomposition of clay minerals into SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ on the one hand, and of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) at about 900 °C to leave calcium oxide (CaO, lime) liberating CO₂, on the other hand. The latter process is known as calcination. This is followed by the clinkering process, in which the CaO reacts at high temperature (typically 1450 °C) with silica, alumina, and ferrous oxide to form the silicates, aluminates, and ferrites of calcium. The resultant clinker is then ground together with gypsum and other additives to produce cement. Naturally occurring calcareous deposits such as limestone, marl or chalk provide calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) and extracted from quarries, often located close to the cement plants. Very small amounts of "corrective" additives such as re ores or clay can be required to compensate Fe₂O₃, Al₂O₃ & SiO₂ to ensure chemical composition. Raw limestone is transported to crushers for breaching down into smaller pieces. Mixing of different raw materials in fixed proportion to attain specific chemical composition and the crushed pieces are then milled together to produce "raw meal" the quality of cement depends on the chemistry of raw meal, which is monitored & controlled carefully. A pre heater is series of vertical mounted cyclone from where feed is passed coming into contact with wet gases moving antidiagonal swirling hot kiln exhaust gases moving in the opposite direction. In these cyclones, thermal energy is recovered from the hot flue gases and the raw meal is preheated before it enters the kiln, so the necessary chemical reaction occurs faster and more efficiently. The precalciner meal then enters the kiln. Fuel is fired directly into the kiln to reach temperature of up to 1450 °C as the kiln rotates, at 3-5 RPM, times per minute, the meal slides & vemes in hotter zone at other and the vigorous heat account to various physical & chemical reactions producing clinker as product.

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